

Farmers' problems and self-reliance
: A study of Kalong Par Halowa Gaon Village under the Rupahi
Block Development Area of Nagaon District

Mr. Deepjyoti Bora
Student of Geography Department, B.A. 6th Semester
Nowgong College (Autonomous), Nagaon, Assam

Email: -deepjyotibora@dr.com
Contact no: +91 8099037552

ABSTRACT

India is mainly an agricultural country. Agriculture is the most important occupation for most of the Indian families. Assam's 70 % of population are engaged in agriculture. Agricultural products of significant economic value include rice, wheat, potato, tomato, onion, mangoes, sugar-cane, beans, cotton, etc. Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy. Though, with the growth of other sectors, the overall share of agriculture on GDP of the country has decreased. Still, Agriculture continues to play a dominant part in the overall economic scenario of India. Food grain is essential for life. In terms of the state domestic product (SDP), the agriculture sector contributed over 25 per cent of the Assam state income in 2021-22. The study was carried in kalong par Halowa gaon of Nagaon district, Assam. More than 40% of populations in the study area are engaged in agriculture. But in the recent time farmers are facing various problems like poverty, used of modern technology, illiteracy, lack of knowledge about market demandable agricultural commodities, irrigation system, flood, drought etc. Total production of rice in the study area is around 65 ton. Total agricultural land in the area is 204.04 hector. Therefore to compensate the various problems in agriculture, most of people in the area are now engaged in other occupations like defence, salesman, entrepreneur, company worker etc. This has a huge impact on self-reliance of the farmers. About 20 % of the villagers are employed in the private sector in other states of India. The study is carried out by using primary data collected from the field survey. The main objective of the study is to find the agricultural problems faced by the people of Kalong Par Halowa Gaon, and their self reliance status.

Keywords: livelihood, agriculture, self reliance

INTRODUCTION

In Assam around 60% of the state's population relies on agriculture as farmers or as agricultural labour. But almost all the farmers faces many problems like poverty, lack of knowledge about modern technology, illiteracy etc. In my study area i.e; Kalong Par Halowa Gaon Village under the Rupahi Block Development Area of Nagaon District, Assam

Their income, standard of living, social status is very low. Increase the number of rural farmer in this study area due to increasing the size population, decline of cottage and village industries, evictions of small farmers, deforestation etc. As a result the farmer of this area faces many problems such as poverty, lack of knowledge, about modern technology, lack of knowledge about market demandable agricultural commodities. In Nagaon district of Assam, agriculture and its allied activities played an important role in the socio-economic development as this sector is considered as a major contributor towards the district economy. Agriculture is considered the backbone of rural economy of the district as it provides livelihoods of rural people. The parallel deposit the availability of irrigation systems in villages, the extensive development in agriculture has been possible. This is because most of the people in the village do not have government jobs and they work as labor in other states. However some people in the village have themselves in business, barbershop and other occupations. The old people here are not very educated but some people are educated. There is a passion for education among the youth of village today. Although not all the children in the village are educated in higher education, but every child is educated. Currently, the illiteracy rate in village is 0. The village is self reliant and has become its backbone at present. Women's group in the village. These women's groups have made various items and strengthened the village economy as well as themselves in the market. Livelihood is a means of securing the necessities of life. It is a means of support and subsistence. Livelihood is defined as a set of activities which involves securing the capacity to acquire above necessities working either individually or as a group by using resources (both human and material) to meet the needs water, food, medicine, shelter, clothing and self lives on another person.

Study area

Kalong Par Halowa Gaon Village is situated in Nagaon District, Assam. Which latitude is 26.3756 and longitude is 92.79345. As the area is located on the bank of Kalong River therefore the fertile alluvial plain has been made rich agricultural activities within the are and

rice, soybeans are extensively cultivated in this region. Like other district of Assam, the traditional mode of agriculture has been carried out by the people of this region. On the basis of the growing season two types crops are practiced by the farmers which are Kharif crops and rabi crops. Kharif crops are cultivated in summer and harvested in winter and on the other hand rabi crops are cultivated in winter and harvested in early summer. However Rabi cultivation is rarely practiced here. In this village has more than 220 households.

OBJECTIVE

- (1) To know the income and productivity of the farmers.
- (2) To know the effect of family size and educational status of the rural farmers
- (3) To examine various valued and unvalued works of area.
- (4) To assess the self reliance status of study area.

METHODOLOGY

The study is based on primary data and the target group population comprises of adult people belonging to 18-60 years age group and five (5) farmers were randomly selected from the surveyed village. For secondary data, various topic related books, internet, research publication, news papers etc. are used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Condition of Rural Farmers in The Study Area

Condition Of Rural Farmers In The Study Area The Kalong Par Halowa Gaon Village under the Rupahi Block Development Area of Nagaon District. It is 12 kms in the North-East direction of Nagaon town. The total area of the Halowa Gaon village is one and half square kilometer. The total population of the village is about 1207 In this village 100 percent population are Hindu communities. The climatic condition of the surveyed village is almost same with Nagaon districts. The average temperature of the village is 38°c and average temperature in winter is 12° to 13° c. The amount of average annual rainfall ranges between 90 cm to 120 cm and rainy season is long about 60 days. The surveyed village is mainly under alluvial soil because it is flood affected area by tributary Kolong. Generally the economic condition of rural farmers depends on many factors viz. level of productivity, rate of literacy, knowledge of new machineries, use of new inputs, farm size, family size, flood and drought in the previous year etc. In table we saw the distribution of farmer by age

Table No: 1 Age Distribution of Farmers in the Study Area

Age Distribution of Farmers in the Study Area	
Age groups	Percentage total (N=14)
20-30	0(0%)
31-40	3(21.4%)
41-50	9(64.28%)
51 and above	2(14.28%)

(Primary Data Collected from filed Survey 2022)

Generally the economic condition of rural farmers depends on many factors viz. level of productivity, rate of literacy, knowledge of new machineries, use of new inputs, farm size, family size, flood and drought in the previous year etc. In table we found that the entire variable except specification

Table No: 2 Regression of Farmers Income on Different Factors

Regression of Farmers Income on Different Factors		
SI No.	Regression of Farmers income on	Percentage total
1	Educational status	14%
2	Farm size	34%
3	Productivity	25%
4	Fertilizer	7%
5	Pesticide	4%
6	Natural calamities	16%

(Primary Data Collected from filed Survey 2022)

From this analysis we came to know that the condition of farmers in the study area is worst due to their lack of farming land, their low literacy rate, poor knowledge of mechanisation, inadequate use of new inputs, etc.

Study on Factors Responsible for Shifting of Rural Youth from Agriculture to other Occupation

The results related to push and pull factors responsible for the migration behavior of the rural youth of Kalong Par Halowa Gaon Village

Table No: 3 Push factor for shifting from agriculture

Push factor for shifting	No	Percentage
Percentage Rank Unemployment and under Employment in rural areas and poverty	8	13.55
Lack of remunerative price for agricultural Commodities in the market	6	10.16
Lack of institutions for higher education	9	15.25
Conversion of agricultural lands into plots	0	0
Labour problem	6	10.16
Burden of loan	2	3.38
Lack of remunerative non agricultural jobs in rural settings	4	6.77
Lack of infrastructure facilities	3	5.08
Drought and scarcity of water	8	13.55
Non availability of inputs in required time	13	22.03

(Primary Data Collected from filed Survey 2022)

Push factors

It could be observed from the table we observed that majority of the respondents (75.00 per cent) in the study area expressed that they were paid lower wages for the agricultural work like land preparation, sowing, planting, weeding and harvesting, which is not sufficient to run their life. This might be the major economic push factor, which leads to shifting. Majority of the respondents expressed that non availability of inputs in the appropriate time and lack of information from the government about the input supply, which affects the crop cultivation. While overseeing the educational level of the respondents it was found to be higher literacy level. However, respondents need for higher educational facilities to enrich their knowledge

for better job might be one of the push factors as felt by 15.25 per cent of the respondents for shifting. Lack of industries, factories and value added units in the study area is one the push factors for the 6.77 per cent of the respondents shifting their mind set for want of jobs and better income. Due to the increase in population, the basic infrastructure facilities and living conditions become worsened in rural areas, which tends the youth (5.08 per cent) to diversify their occupations.

Table No: 4 Pull factor for shifting from agriculture

Pull factor for shifting	No	Percentage
Rank High income	7	9.3
Higher level of educational facilities	5	6.66
Lower risk from natural hazards	0	0
Employment opportunities	34	45.33
Better social life and standard of living	12	16
Availability of good infrastructure facilities	17	22.66

(Primary Data Collected from filed Survey 2022)

Pull factor

Majority of the respondents (61.66 per cent) are involved in differential occupations, which had given more income generation and better standard of living is an another reason for shifting from agriculture. Availability of infrastructure facilities such as hospitals, schools and marketing facilities attracted 22.66 per cent of the rural youth for shifting. In order to overcome the severe water scarcity existed in the study area, rural youth tend to escape from agriculture and also stated that less risk was involved in the non agricultural jobs (0 per cent) might be one of the pull factors for shifting. Better jobs and high income ultimately attracted rural youth towards better social life and standard of living might be one of the pull factors for 45.33per cent of respondents. Lack of educational facilities in the study area is one of push factor, which primarily attracted 6.66 percent of the respondents to get more educational opportunities and facilities through shifting

Some Important aspects through which we can revive the agricultural sector

1. Need to Engage Agricultural Graduates in rural Areas: Central govt. has launched many schemes in agricultural field. In Assam it is also important to develop agri – clinics, agri- business etc. The scheme of agriclincs and agri-business centers was launched in 2002 as a follow up of finance Minister’s Budget speech for 2001. The aim of this scheme was to provide extension services to the farming community and to provide self – employment opportunities to the agriculture graduates. In rural areas of Assam the youth can take different projects and loan facilities’ from different banks, NGO,s etc.

2. Vocational Training and extension services: The tool for teaching different skills for agriculture and other activities are very important for the Youth. It will increase the employment facilities of the youth in rural areas.

3. Improving the technical Knowledge among the Youth: In the era of Science and Technology the Youth’s power should be increase with the new technologies. In rural areas of Assam digital awareness should be improved. Youth should be able to get the latest information related to different job, career etc. with the help of Mobile, Internet, E-mail, Websites etc.

4. Strengthen the rural health care facilities: A large number of rural people have faced many problems due to the lack of appropriate health facilities in the villages. In rural areas health care centre, Hospitals etc. should be established by the government.

5. Employment facilities should be increased : Unemployment is the main problem in the rural areas of Assam. Government should take initiative in this regard to solve this problem. New employment policy should be implemented in various sectors.

6. Improvement of the infrastructure facilities of Education: Education is the main key for development of a country. Every individual of the society should be educated for developing a country.

7. Increase the Infrastructure facilities in the society: In rural areas of Assam there are so many problems in different areas. These should be improved properly. Only the development of urban areas cannot lead the development of a nation. Therefore rural areas should be developed like- situation of transportation, communication, electricity, computer & internet facilities, etc.

8. Migration: For removing this problem employment facilities should be improved in the rural areas of our country specially for the youth in Assam.

9. Regular funds for rural areas should be provided: The government fund should be release equally in a high rate to the rural areas of Assam.

10. Development of Awareness about education: Awareness is very important to develop education, empowerment, increasing knowledge etc

11. Improvement of Market facilities in Rural area: For the Youths businessmen or farmer it is a big problem in the rural area of Assam that they have not get sufficient type of Market for selling their goods. Government,& NGO,s can provide this facilities to the Youth.

II. Status of self reliance people in study area

Much of the works done by people are either undervalued or unvalued. This is one of the many reasons responsible for the socioeconomic backwardness of people in many developing countries of the world. The present study, therefore, attempts to assess the livelihood patterns and the nature of the valued and unvalued works of the people in Kalong Par Halowa Gaon Village under the Rupahi Block Development Area of Nagaon District

Table No: 5 Current Valued Livelihood of people (Participation in percentage)

Nature of work done	Percentage of people doing	Average income per month	Percentage of satisfaction from job
Teachers in Educational Institutions	10	35885.71	88.5
Doctor	2	80000	94
Defence	20	3857.20	80
Salesmen	5	3214.67	70.25
Care Taker	2	2000	40
Nursing	5	12890.50	83.60
Tuition	6	2560	73.25
Agent of insurance company	2	10000	60
Tailoring	2	6000	65
Cooking	3	5000	70
Weaving	6	3250.70	67.5
Company worker	16	12000	68
Agricultural labour	18	2150	51
Other	3	-	-

(Primary Data Collected from filed Survey 2022)

Table-5 throws light on the valued livelihoods of respondent women as found at the time of survey. Out of total 12 percent of peoples are doing the jobs of teaching in educational institutions. Their average income per month is Rs. 35885.71 and their average job satisfaction level is 88.5 percent. Other occupations combined employ only 38% of the population in agriculture.

Table No: 6 Current Unvalued Livelihood of people (Participation in percentage)

Types of work done	Percentage of people doing unvalued work(Specially Women)	
	Regular basis	Temporary basis
Cooking	96.5	3.5
Family care	99	1
Cleaning activities	96.26	3.75
Weaving	4.69	25.36
Gardening	0	43
Woolen work	0	25.5
Embroidery	0	12

(Primary Data Collected from filed Survey 2022)

From the Table it is seen that out of 300 respondents 96.5 percent women do cooking on regular basis and only 3.5 percent women are doing it on temporary basis; 99 percent women are found engaged in care giving for their family members on regular basis by spending time day and just only 1 percent women do it on temporary basis..

III. Examples of people of Kalong Par Halowa Gaon becoming self-reliant

1. Fishery

2. Women Self Help Groups.

One of the ways of self-reliance of the villagers is through the fisheries in the villages. Most of the villagers have their own ponds and people raise fish in those ponds. About approximately 363 kg of fish are caught annually from all the ponds in the village. The villagers earn about lakhs of rupees annually from market through fishery. Village women's groups are involved in various activities. It places great emphasis on women's empowerment. These women's groups exchange loans and make various items like weaving clothes, woolen clothes, pickles etc. at home and release them for sale in the market. These women's groups have been occupying a significant portion of the markets.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the above study we can say that the chronic poverty, illiteracy, lack of mechanization, , lack of capital formation, flood and drought, poor agricultural marketing facilities, lack of knowledge about demandable crops or more appropriately the absence of commercialization of agriculture sector are the main problems of the rural farmers. Therefore, if we can focus more on agriculture through scientific methods, it will help in eradicating food

shortages and poverty. In addition, it is necessary to monitor whether the government schemes are being enjoyed by the right beneficiaries. In addition, people need to be made aware, and trained to become self-reliant. Women should be empowered and made self-reliant by providing training to them through various types of NGOs. Special training on pig farming, poultry farming, fish farming, dairy production etc. should be provided.

REFERENCES

1. Bhagabati, A.K (1990): Spatial Analysis of Small- Scale Agriculture in Assam : A Case Study of Nalbari District, Unpublished Ph.d thesis Gauhati University, Guwahati.
2. Dhar, P. K. Axomor arthanitir ruprekha (The Economy of Assam). Kalyani Publishers: Ludhiana, 1994.
3. Datta, L (1984): Agricultural Occupance of Nowgong District, Unpublished Ph.d thesis Gauhati University, Guwahati
5. Das, S. K. (2012), "Women at the 21st Century: A reflection on the status and security of women in Assam", Journal of Alternative Perspectives in the Social Sciences, Vol. 3, No 4, Pp. 111-138
6. Gupta, I. and A. Mitra. 2002. Rural Migrants and Labour Segmentation, Micro-level Evidence from Delhi Slums. Economic and Political Weekly. January 12, p:163-168.
7. Knutson, R. D., J.B. Penn, and Barry L. Flinchbaugh. Agricultural and Food Policy. 4th ed., Prentice Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, 1998.
8. Kalita, G (2015): Socio- Spatial Variation of Agricultural Development in Darrang District, Assam: A geographical analysis, Unpublished Ph.d thesis Gauhati University, Guwahati.
9. Monalisha Mili , (2018) Empowerment of Women by Self-help Groups in Boginadi Block of Lakhimpur District, Assam, INDIAN SCIENCE CRUISER , Volume 32 ,No 5
10. Phukan, A. K. Z (ed.). Axomor arthaniti, 1997 (The Economy of Assam, 1997). Buniyad: Guwahati, 1997.